

4B Exposing metadata

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📌 Introduction

In this section we describe the FAIR Data Point (FDP) and its role in data onboarding. We also provide information about the various ways of implementing an FDP in your institute. Note that this page is intended for general audiences.

e by institute/node if you are using their infrastructure.

Fig. 1: General overview of the Implementation (step 4) of the onboarding. Note that some implementation steps might (FDP implementation, automation etc.) be done by institute/node if you are using their infrastructure.

FAIR Data Point

A FAIR Data Point Is a server-side application that exposes metadata following the FAIR principles. By adhering to FAIR principles, data providers can ensure that their data is accessible, understandable and usable by others while respecting privacy and ethical considerations. This promotes greater transparency and accountability in data sharing efforts, fostering more equitable and responsible use of data for research, innovation and decision-making. FDP specification is based on widely accepted semantic metadata standards DCAT ([4A Metadata mapping](#)) .

Here is a short video (2:05) from [Fair Enough](#) that explains what and FDP is:

Implement a FAIR Data Point

 FDP implementation requires expert knowledge and likely need to be done by a data manager, data steward or equivalent.

In principle there are several ways for implementation of an FDP. In general, we recommend an implementation as close to the source of the data as possible to ensure that the data is accurate and updated. This would be a local deployment of an FDP ([4B_1b FDP reference implementation](#)) at your institute or using an existing implementation of an FDP protocol within a tool your institute uses such as Molgenis or Castor (A list of implementations can be found [here](#)) [4B_1a Expose your local system](#) .

In some cases, an FDP is already present within an institute and can be used for onboarding. If you are not sure if a local FDP is available, contact Health-RI service desk servicedesk@health-ri.nl.

If an FDP implementation is not possible due to, for example; security issues, there is an option of using a central FDP. In general, this way is not preferred as it uses manual data entry, is removed from the data source and requires regular updates. You can find more information about this path here: [4B_1c Central FDP](#)

Populate a FAIR Data Point

After a FDP implementation, you are ready to populate the FDP with your metadata [4B_2 Metadata entry into an FDP](#) .

Firstly, the HRI shacled files need to be imported to the FDP: [4B_2 Importing shacl files in the FDP - Front end](#)

Then your metadata can be imported, there are several ways to do this. First is manual entry ([4B_2 Metadata entry into an FDP](#))

We do not recommend this path as it does require manual input and is not scalable. Therefore we recommend to automate your input: [4B_2a Automate export from your local system](#) for example using the python package SeMPyRO: [4B_2b Example python code to upload metadata to FDP](#) .

Here is a video (4:47) explaining the deployment of an FDP by [Fair Enough](#) :

▶ [How to deploy a FAIR Data Point in your local computer](#)

How to deploy a FAIR Data Point in your local computer

✔ Next steps

If you have an FDP and compliant metadata ([4A Metadata mapping](#)) within your FDP, the data can be harvested by the National Catalogue [5. Metadata harvesting](#).

📘 Additional resources

1. **An original paper describing an FDP:** Luiz Olavo Bonino da Silva Santos, Kees Burger, Rajaram Kaliyaperumal, Mark D. Wilkinson; FAIR Data Point: A FAIR-Oriented Approach for Metadata Publication. *Data Intelligence* 2023; 5 (1): 163–183. doi: [FAIR Data Point: A FAIR-Oriented Approach for Metadata Publication](#)
2. [Video: Technical details on DCAT AP and FAIR Datapoints \(Health-RI\)](#)
3. [FAIR Data Point](#) - Description and list of implementations
4. [GitHub - FAIRDataTeam/FAIRDataPoint-Spec: Specification for the FAIR DataPoint](#)
5. [FAIR Data Point specifications](#)

Metroline pages (note: some pages are under development):

[Metroline Step: Transform and expose FAIR \(meta\)data](#)

[Metroline Step: Define access conditions](#)

💬 Questions?

If you have questions about the onboarding process or would like to learn more. Reach out to our [Health-RI Servicedesk | Health-RI](#)

✉ servicedesk@health-ri.nl